

REFUGEE WATCH

A South Asian Journal on Forced Migration

**Contemporary Wars and Politics of Dispossession:
Afghanistan and Ukraine**

60

Mahanirban Calcutta Research Group
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Report

Ukraine War Refugees and Human Rights in a Global Context

By

**Alex Aleinikoff, Ayşe Çağlar, Grażyna Baranowska,
Olena Fedyuk, Randall Hansen ***

The massive displacement the Ukraine War unleashed had its effects within a global context. Russia's invasion of Ukraine is often seen as pivotal in terms of its impact on the global order of power, Europe's understanding of itself and its future, and on the location of Russia, among others. Since World War II, the unprecedented displacement that this war unleashed in Europe means that we must situate it within a global context and address the possible transformations they indicate for the future. Ukrainians fleeing the war are called refugees in our daily languages, but they are not officially recognized as refugees and instead have temporary protection status. This status allows Ukrainians to enter European Union (EU) Member States and access rights, the labour market, education, health, etc. Although temporary protection is a double-edged sword and comes with its restrictions, this status raised

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questions in the public debate and scholarship about the 'unequal/special treatment' of displaced groups. The debates considered the temporary protection status awarded to Ukrainians in contrast to the restricted border regimes many other recently forcefully displaced groups faced in Europe, such as those fleeing from the wars in Afghanistan and Syria. Such comparisons about the status of the displaced tend to underline the 'unique' or 'singular' aspects of this displacement and emplacement of Ukrainian refugees and this war.

Q. Ayşe Çağlar: Where do we locate the commonalities between those groups displaced from Ukraine and those displaced in other parts of the world? How do we see any transformation in border and humanitarian regimes and their management for and of the displaced? Is there anything new on that front? And if there is a transformation in the making, what today can be viewed as a hint toward the future?

A. Alex Alenikoff: It is essential to examine how the Ukrainian situation may affect and transform the global refugee regime. We are seeing mixed signals around the world. More than six million Ukrainians have been welcomed in Europe, and at the same time that the United Kingdom is trying to send asylum seekers to Rwanda; in the United States, President Biden has reversed Donald Trump's dramatic cut in refugee admissions but has kept in place the so-called Title 42 regulations that permit the summary expulsion of anybody arriving in the border—nominally in the name of protection against Covid but in reality to stem the flow of asylum-seekers to the south-west border. So too, we see billions of dollars being raised for humanitarian relief in Ukraine while other significant and long-standing displacement situations are underfunded or ignored. Globally, the number of persons displaced within and outside their countries of origin now exceeds one hundred million. So, how does Ukraine fit into this scenario? In some ways, the Ukraine situation shows the one significant way the refugee regime works well: it provides initial safety to those who flee their homes across an international border. We tend to focus on the disparate treatment afforded Afghans and Ukrainians in the EU, but if we look from a different perspective, the international refugee regime does respond pretty well to flight across borders to countries of first asylum. So, Syrians were provided safety in Jordan, Lebanon, and Turkey; thousands of Rohingyas were permitted to enter Bangladesh. In the same way, the Ukrainians could go to Poland and other European states. The difficulty for the Global North and the EU is the secondary flow from countries of first asylum. There were very few Syrians who fled directly from Syria to the EU. They had spent three or four years in neighboring states of Syria; eventually, they used up their resources and were not locally integrated in a formal sense, so they began to look for other places to go.

There have been innovations in the Ukrainian response, some of which may carry forward. Let me mention first, the role of private sponsorship. Typically, the resettlement of refugees has been a state-run function. For some years now, Canada has been using a form of private sponsorship where groups of Canadians can sponsor refugee admissions.

What we have now seen in the EU context is a massive role of private sponsorship and assistance. Ukrainians were not put into refugee camps; there were some reception centres where people stayed for a few days or a week or two until they could go elsewhere. But most found shelter and support from private persons and groups. Similarly, in the United States, tens of thousands of Afghans—“paroled” into the US—were welcomed by private families. The State Department will also formalize private sponsorship of refugees this year.

The second important development is increased mobility for refugees. Under the temporary protection directive, Ukrainians can choose the country where they will be granted temporary protection. Furthermore, the EU states have waived the requirement that persons remain in those states. So Ukrainians are generally able to move into the EU, which is quite a different policy than is established for other refugee groups in Europe and around the world. As is well known, most refugees remain trapped in countries of first asylum—a situation I have called the phenomenon of “the second in exile.” They find themselves stuck because they can’t go home (because the conflict has not ended); they are not permitted to be locally integrated into the economy and society of the hosting state, and very few resettlement spots exist. So, I have argued for a while now that enhancing mobility for refugees should be a goal of the system—enabling them to travel to places where they can take care of themselves, start their lives over, be reunited with family, and go to school. I don't think you will see it globally, but it could develop regionally, as has appeared to happen in the EU vis-à-vis Ukrainians.

Now a word on the relationship between human rights and refugee law. They exist side by side, overlap, and are concerned with similar issues, but they have different norms and structures for their enforcement. Scholars have attempted to morph refugee law into applied human rights law. It hasn't been fully adopted, and I don't think it will be entirely successful. Nonetheless, we need to adopt a broader conception of “people of concern”—to consider all aspects of displacement—and to move beyond the definition of refugee available in the 1951 Convention. One route would be to consider whether there is a human right to stay home that may be violated when conflicts, violence, climate change, and other environmental events cause the flight. Also, is there a human right not to be returned to danger? This is the principle of *non-refoulement*, so crucial to refugee law. But it applies in refugee law only if you can show you are a refugee—that is if you can show a well-founded fear of persecution on one of five particular grounds. The norm of *non-refoulement* doesn't protect people being forced from their homes due to human rights abuses or the effects of climate change. And might we be able to develop a human right to the mobility I have just described? These changes will come through applying a broader notion of human rights law. Obviously, this is not the ideal time to suggest identifying new human rights. Because the Ukraine War is a classic refugee situation, with an invading country forcing people out of their homes, it doesn't give rise to discussions of these expansions of human rights law—although it may help to transform the refugee regime in the ways I mentioned.

Q. Ayşe Çağlar: By adopting a common legal framework (temporary protection) and allowing Ukrainians fleeing Ukraine to cross EU national borders, the EU had shown a very coordinated performance, especially if we compare it to the reactions during the 2015 “refugee crisis”. What kind of light does the Ukraine War shed on the changing nature of borders within the EU, within Europe, but also elsewhere? Cultural narratives had been evoked in various ways about the displaced, their differentiated inclusions, and humanitarianism, but also in framing the exclusions. As someone who had worked on the post-Second World War narratives, how do you locate those, if you wish to say, 'cultural civilizational narratives' that surface through the war, and how does the 2015 “refugee crisis” figure in these narratives and imaginaries? Is there anything new about the unequal treatment of different displaced groups?

A. Randall Hansen: I will take these questions in reverse order. On differential treatment, the response that you have seen on Twitter and in the press suggests that there is something fundamentally different about the Ukrainian refugee crisis; this reaction, it seems to me, is entirely wrong. To paraphrase Erich Remarque, there is nothing new in the West. The current refugee crisis in Europe is like most crises we have experienced. Everywhere, the vast majority of refugees flee not persecution of the sort scene in the 1930s (when, for instance, a German-Jewish Professor was fired for being Jewish) but instead invading armies. This is precisely what is happening in Europe. What Slovakia, Poland, and Romania did (for Ukrainians) was exactly what Lebanon, Jordan, and Turkey did (for Syrians). It's what every country does. When a contiguous country is a massive refugee-producing country and refugees are coming to you *en masse*, you have two choices—you open the border, or you open fire. Almost every country opens its border.

But borders do matter. At the moment, we have, on the one hand, a massive reconfiguration of borders in the sense that Russia unilaterally violated the border for the first time since 1945 by attempting to change the border through force. At the same time, in the face of massive refugee flows, most European countries have opened their borders—that is, suspended borders altogether. On the other hand, we are fighting this war for many reasons, but one is maintaining the sanctity of the Ukraine-Russia border. So, there is a complex process of collapsing yet reinforcing borders.

Let me make a final comment on civilizational discourse. The most obvious way this is emerging is concerning the enemy—Russia. There is a great tendency among commentators to essentialize Russia as inherently imperialist, inherently expansionist, inherently eliminationist, inherently murderous, and so on. It is exactly what we heard before in the 1930s and 1940s about the Germans.

Parochially, the response among faculty in the European Centre, which I have just stopped directing, was to call for an end to all cooperation with Russia and Russians. As ever, in the case of academic boycotts, I was opposed because the last thing we should do is stop talking to our colleagues.

Q. Ayşe Çağlar: There is an emphasis placed on the cultural and religious characteristics of the people fleeing wars in public debates on the reasons behind their ‘special treatment’ in the European countries they take refuge. How do these narratives affect the regulation of borders? With the differential treatment of the displaced at the borders, the Polish border plays a specific role in these discussions. It remains open for the displaced Ukrainians, but thousands of those displaced from Syria and Afghanistan and fleeing from war elsewhere are stuck at the Belarus-Polish border. So, how has this simultaneous openness and closure of the borders to the forcefully displaced enacted in laws? Where do you see such detentions being anchored in the laws? How do those borders figure for the displaced non-Ukrainian citizens from Ukraine, the Third Country nationals fleeing from Ukraine? Many NGOs are working on the borders assisting the displaced. What does this contradictory working of the Polish border mean for the NGOs working for the displaced? What do these border asymmetries mean for the NGOs involved in providing aid and assistance to the displaced?

A: Grażyna Baranowska: Firstly, I would like to point out one uniqueness of the Ukrainian situation, probably more of an EU uniqueness. Secondly, I will situate the Ukrainian refugee situation against the humanitarian crisis on the Belarus-EU border. But before I do that, let me quickly respond to your question on NGOs operating at the Polish eastern border. Poland has a 500kms long border with Ukraine and 400kms with Belarus, both of which have been in the light of attention for the last year. At both borders people are trying to enter Poland to seek refuge, but—as we know—only at the Ukrainian border is this efficiently and safely done. NGOs and volunteers are operating to help people at the borders, but they are intimidated and not allowed to help at the Belarusian border while cherished for the work they have been doing at the Ukrainian border. Criminal charges have been brought against people helping at the Belarusian border. It is often the same NGOs operating at both borders and now moving on from this to the one uniqueness of the situation. The Ukrainians fleeing the war could quickly enter the EU because they did not have to apply for a visa. This possibility to travel visa-free to the EU was introduced in 2017. It did not start with the Ukraine War. That gave the EU a different perspective because, in other contexts, the major challenge of refugee seekers is to reach the EU safely, as they cannot obtain a visa to do so. There are even countries where the acceptance rate of refugee applications is exceptionally high, but they have virtually no way to enter the EU regularly, for example, Eritrea. So, the only way for them to reach the EU safely is to engage themselves in life-threatening situations and take perilous routes. But once they reach the EU, they have safety and support. This is not the case for Ukrainians because they could enter the EU without applying for a visa. Consequently, what the EU was deciding upon after February 24, 2022, was not whether or not to make it possible for people to cross the border, but what to do once they have

entered. What I wish this situation would trigger in the European context would be a discussion about extending visa-free traveling to the EU. This would establish better and safer ways to respond to the crisis. Secondly, discuss that fleeing war or persecution does not have to be life-threatening. We need to repeat that because people are not dying when fleeing war in Ukraine, which should hold true for those fleeing from other countries as well, but it doesn't. So, this brings me to compare the situations at the two Polish borders—Ukraine and Belarus. I think Poland is an interesting case study because, in 2015, Poland was at the forefront of the EU countries opposing refugees and their relocation. The events taking place since 2021, which I call the humanitarian crisis at the Polish-Belarusian border, were initiated by the Lukashenko regime that brought people to and through the border. The humanitarian crisis was also triggered by the response of the Polish state, which was to push those people back to Belarus. Under domestic and international laws, this should not have happened. Their claims and needs should have been assessed once they were in Poland. That should have happened, but it did not. The practice on the ground pushed them back, and it was grounded in the domestic laws within a couple of weeks. Other laws were also adopted very quickly. For example, a state of emergency denied journalists and humanitarian help to enter the area. While the legal response to the humanitarian crisis at the Polish-Belarusian border was concentrated on denying them service, just a couple of months later, the Polish state responded to people fleeing Ukraine by quickly adopting laws to support them. For example, they have the same health care same as Polish citizens, access to education, and access to childcare benefits. The situation of people fleeing Ukraine in Poland is substantially better than other refugees. The legal frameworks responding to people fleeing through the Belarus border and the war in Ukraine are in strong opposition. There is massive support for both of those two policies. Recently, I have found research by Krawatzek and Goldstein (*Poles in Times of Dramatic Change: Refugees, Identity and Social Engagement* (zois-berlin.de) showing that 50 per cent of young people Poles agree with the statement that Poland should take in as many people fleeing the Ukrainian War as necessary. In comparison, over 60 per cent of them argue that people stranded at the Polish-Belarusian border should not even be able to apply for asylum. This shows strong support concerning both the politics of Ukraine and the Polish-Belarusian border.

A. Randall Hansen: There is a logic to the claim that Ukrainians are being treated better than Syrians—the Ukrainians were welcomed in Poland, whereas Syrians were not. But let's remember that the *temporary protection* status the Ukrainians are receiving is less generous than the *refugee status* that the Syrians received. The Ukrainians got three years of temporary protection, *not* refugee status, which Germany, Sweden, and Austria chiefly accorded to 1.2 million Syrians.

Q. Ayşe Çağlar: These legal frameworks show the complexity concerning the Ukrainian refugees in Poland and that they are better off than other refugees in terms of their rights and benefits. Similarly, in many other places like Turkey, access to education, healthcare,

childcare, etc., is present, but there is no access to the refugee's rights to resettlement for those under temporary protection. This creates different kinds of tensions in the countries and not yet in Poland.

The distributive scheme often goes parallel with moral hierarchies and representations, as well as with the permeability of the EU border on constructions of distinction between deserving refugees and undeserving economic migrants. These juxtapositions are more complex in relation to the Ukrainians in Europe because Ukraine has a long history of out-migration, displacement, and exile. Since 1991, especially Ukrainian migrants have been going to different countries in Europe, working in the care sector and the service industries as labourers. How are these migrants anchored in the current narratives in terms of the assistance programmes vis-à-vis the currently displaced because the others were under the category of economic migrants, and some of them were undocumented, and now we have different groups of displaced Ukrainians in Europe? What happens to their access to rights concerning the newcomers? What happens to their status and access to rights? How did 'class' figure there? And finally, former migrants/refugees always provide critical networks to the newcomers in terms of reaching institutions, and knowledge, among others. Given that civilian and voluntary networks play a significant role in assisting the displaced, what kinds of collaborations, but also tensions do you see there?

A. Olena Fedyuk: I want to add a slightly different perspective to the original question of what is or might be different in terms of the practical situation that we see unfolding with the reception of people who flee the war in Ukraine. It is related to the vital role of various forms of labour migration from Ukraine. Since the collapse of the Soviet Union in 1991 and the opening up of the Iron Curtain, we have had all possible forms of mobility for primarily economic reasons labeled as labour migration and are well-documented in numerous migration studies works. We had shuttle migration, short-term migration, and long-term migration. We had migration for settlement. We had wide variations in migration in terms of demographics too. We had a similar kind of variety in migration with regard to age and gender, even if differentiated by destination countries. For instance, we have quite unequal migratory flows from countries in terms of gender composition, like the southern European welfare-modeled countries relying heavily on female laborers in terms of reproducing their society through care work or domestic work. But overall, mobility was growing and maturing and developing complex transnational placemaking in the last 30 years with remarkably diverse local connections. All these flows are most often labeled as labour migration, driven purely by economic motivation, and one thing which is very often overlooked in this perspective is that this migration was happening in response to tremendous geo-political and political economy changes but also in response to changes in social structures, ideological and moral opinions and perceptions. In terms of ideologies, all these waves have

left Ukraine in its specific political-economic climate; these people have been taking their set of ideological visions about Ukraine and its future abroad with them. Thus besides sending their economic remittances back home, they have also been engaged back in Ukraine through some quiet direct political action. These processes and commitment are what I wanted to highlight here: many times, migration studies research agenda in connection with Ukrainian migration undermined and looked at various forms of transnational political participation of Ukrainian labour migrants. Even though we have extensive evidence of high political mobilization during all the periods of domestic crises, during the Orange Revolution, even irregular migrants from Ukraine were organising to help Ukrainian citizens abroad to participate in the voting and organising public protests in the squares of the receiving countries. We have seen this again during Maidan; tremendous mobilization around the Revolution of Dignity (again, pointing to political and ideological values) as in forming the local communities, influencing the local political opinion in the receiving countries through protests, information campaigns, but also massive support through donations, volunteering, direct support to the Ukrainian Army.

And this brings me to the current situation when the Russian war on Ukraine has further and drastically fragmented the experience of people fleeing this war. We must remember that people with different backgrounds have been displaced and set on the move. As with every form of mobility, we must not forget that first, people who could afford it started to move, and in this case, precisely the people who had the social capital and some network that guided their flight. Let's say this is not based on any numerical research but on my experience of volunteering for the first couple of months in Budapest. The most frequent phrase I had to translate for the people arriving at the train station was how to buy tickets for someplace else where they had some connections. Everyone in the first few months knew where they were going, and of course, if you look at the UNHCR numbers, the number of people who moved to different countries very often mirrored the previously established labour migration corridors. The tremendous role of these previously established labour migrants' networks and experience of political mobilisation and civic organisation played a crucial role in supporting this mobility. Europe and European states have opened their borders, and many local initiatives have provided initial relief from the humanitarian catastrophe of the war. But it is the already existing networks of labour migrants that have received the primary financial, social and emotional pressure in terms of receiving and integrating these people. So, through the several examples of the people I worked with and followed throughout the years of my research, I saw multiple repetitions of similar situations. To give it a simplified version, for example, I knew people who work in the care economy in Italy who financed the flee of their mother, daughter, and grandchildren to Italy. So now they have found them accommodation, have agreed with their employers to find a way to settle them. But on top of all that, they still have to work, and besides just being alone, they have to support another four people and those who have stayed back in Ukraine and could not be mobile. But they still need

support. Even before the war, such transnational support networks were often asymmetrical, as we know from the migration literature. Now they have received much more pressure. Curiously, the arrival of labour migrants' families and other dependents also revealed the real ugly face of the migration regimes, where workers could work so intensely only because their social and family reproduction was removed from them and carried out by their families back in Ukraine. All these workers, who until now seemed to be happy to take extra hours at work, or provide care to a family 24/7 in the receiving country, could not sustain these intense work regimes once they had their own families around. And the same thing happened here in Hungary, where many Ukrainians work through temporary work agencies in the factories: living in worker dorms taking 12-hour-long weekend shifts became unsustainable with the arrival of their families. The moment they received their families, they could not work so "diligently" anymore or found these regimes of intensive exploitation unsustainable with the life-work balance. Similarly, their wages, which allowed them to live and remit in the "labour migrant" mode, proved to be highly insufficient for sustaining a family on an income not based on extra shifts and working hours. Finally, from the legal perspective, people who arrived as labour migrants before February 2022 found themselves uncertain. Some of those people were using biometrical passports for seasonal work trips, and when that status expired, they found themselves in between statuses, unable to switch jobs, renew their permit, and, on top of it, now responsible for the well-being and integration of their newly arrived family members. Therefore, if we want to have a long-term perspective of the needs of the current refugees fleeing Ukraine, we also need to think about the better incorporation of people from the previous labour migration networks.

Conclusion

The Ukrainian War has a cohesive role for Europe and European Values. It is so often underlined that goes beyond cultural divides within. But also, one could see that it also broadens other divides between the Global North and Global South in terms of the reactions, in terms of insistence on keeping the right to be neutral vis-à-vis the economic war waged through coordinated sanctions. Nationalism and anti-colonial sentiments acquired prominence in the political debates.

The Report is a transcript of an online Round Table discussion organised by the Institute for Human Sciences, Vienna, on 'Ukrainian War, Refugees, and Human Rights in a Global Context' on July 6 2022, under its Europe-Asia Research Platform Forced Migration Program in collaboration with the Calcutta Research Group. The panelists were Alex Aleinikoff, Grażyna Baranowska, Olena Fedynuk, and Randall Hansen, and were moderated by Ayşe Çağlar. The discussion is available at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aSO-ORDVrDA&t=3114s>